

***Micrococcus luteus* sma-1, an actinomycetota isolated from a wastewater treatment plant: Evaluation of heavy metals resistance within a genomic framework**

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Abstract

Micrococcus luteus sma-1 is an actinomycetota isolated from a biological reactor in a wastewater treatment plant of the Civac Water Pollution Control Company (ECCACIV), in Morelos, Mexico. Previous studies of this microorganism demonstrated the presence of a clear resistance to various heavy metals such as mercury (Hg), nickel (Ni), tin (Sn), copper (Cu) and lead (Pb) by determining the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), with copper showing the higher MIC value, greater than 40 mM. From the genome sequencing of the bacteria, the genome size was determined to be 2,001 Mbp, with a G+C content of 72.33% mol, with an N50 and L50 of 2596 and 213, respectively. On the other hand, whole genome analysis indicated that *Micrococcus* sp. sma-1 is a member of *Micrococcus luteus*, obtaining a DNA-DNA digital hybridization (dDDH) value greater than 70%. The annotation of the genome of *Micrococcus luteus* sma-1 revealed the presence of 13 genes associated with resistance to toxic metals, which confer resistance to mercury, cobalt, zinc, cadmium, copper and iron. The most notable are *copC*, *copD*, *merA* and *czcD*. These results suggest that *Micrococcus luteus* sma-1 have a potential application in bioremediation due to its resistance to various toxic metals.

Introduction

Currently, heavy metals pollution problem has been increased, making it necessary to find alternatives that can counteract and reduce the effects of contaminated sites (Luo et al. 2020). Lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg) and arsenic (As) are the main polluting metals and, in turn, the most toxic, representing a threat to terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, as well as human health (Kumar et al., 2019). Bioremediation techniques have emerged as a promising alternative to address this problem, as they take advantage of the ability of many organisms, such as bacteria, fungi, algae and plants; to adapt to contaminated environments. These organisms have developed biological defense mechanisms that allow them to biotransform and resist these contaminants, making them the best candidates for restoring contaminated sites (Adams et al., 2015).

Micrococcus is a Gram-positive coccus bacterial genus belonging to the family Micrococcaceae, phylum Actinomycetota. Until now, *Micrococcus* comprises nine validated species (<https://lpsn.dsmz.de/genus/micrococcus>). Recently, the *Micrococcus luteus* group was established including *M. luteus*, *M. aloverae*, *M. endophyticus* and *M. yunannensis* based on

phenotypic characteristics and genomic analysis (Huang et al., 2019). *M. luteus* has been isolated from several hosts and environments, including heavy metals contaminated sites (Román-Ponce et al., 2016, Arroyo-Herrera et al., 2021). Several studies have associated these bacteria with contaminated environments, evidencing their ability to survive in such conditions (Correto et al., 2020).

Nowadays, several studies have evaluated the presence of different heavy metal mechanisms in *Micrococcus* strains conferring resistance to many heavy metals (Puyen et al., 2012, Gunan Yucel et al., 2021) and some of them were identified as genes involved with arsenic (Vijay et al., 2017, Sher et al., 2020, Arroyo-Herrera et al., 2023) and chromium resistance (Arroyo-Herrera et al., 2023).

Previous research revealed resistance to multiple heavy metals, including mercury (Hg), nickel (Ni), tin (Sn), copper (Cu), and lead (Pb), by determining a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). The investigation found that copper had the highest MIC, with a value of >40 mM (Blanco-Mercado, 2022). Therefore, in this study the data obtained from Whole Genomic Sequence (WGS) of this bacterium provides relevant information to carry out its taxonomic identification and to determine the genes involved in heavy metal resistance to understand the mechanism of action and apply them in different bioremediation processes either in soil or water.

Materials and Methods

Sampling site and bacterial isolation

Micrococcus sp. sma-1 was isolated from a biological reactor at the wastewater treatment plant of the Civac Water Pollution Control Company (ECCACIV) in Jiutepec, Morelos, México (18° 52' 14" N, 99° 10' 17" W) For bacteria isolation, 100 mL of wastewater samples were collected in plastic containers, transported to the laboratory and frozen until use. The sample aliquots were diluted 5x in tubes containing 10 mL of distilled water and each dilution (0.1 mL) was spread in triplicate on a nutritive agar medium. The Petri dishes were incubated at 30°C for 48 h. Colonies were counted and single colonies with different morphologies were selected and purified by repeated cross-streaking. The purified bacteria were preserved in 50 % glycerol (w/v) at -80°C (Rojo-Acosta 2020).

DNA isolation, sequence assembly and genomic annotation

The strain was inoculated in 50 mL of Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) medium and incubated at 30°C in an orbital shaker for 18 h. Genomic DNA was recovered using a modified phenol: chloroform protocol proposed by Hoffman and Winston (1987). The strain sma-1 was previously identified as *Micrococcus* sp. using a 16S rRNA sequence (Rojo-Acosta, 2020). The WGS of *Micrococcus* sp. sma-1 was obtained following the procedure indicated by MicrobesNG and using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 with 250-bp paired-end reads. The data quality of the raw sequences was assessed using FastQC software, v 0.12.1 (Wingett & Andrews, 2018). Graphical reports generated by FastQC were reviewed and sequence trimming was performed as necessary using Trimmomatic version 0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014), where adapters were removed. Clean sequences were re-assessed using FastQC to verify improved data quality. Sequences were then assembled “de novo” using SPAdes v 3.15.5 (Bankevich et al., 2012). The assembly quality was then assessed in QUAST v 5.2.0 (Mikheenko et al., 2018) by obtaining metrics such as the number of contigs, total assembly length, N50, N90, L50, L90, RNA genes and protein-coding genes. The assembled genome was annotated and visualized on the RAST platform (Aziz et al., 2008). For taxonomic identification purposes, closely related genomes were downloaded from Ezbiocloud platform (<https://www.ezbiocloud.net/>) and Overall Genomic Relatedness Index (OGRIs) were calculated. The average nucleotide identity (ANI) (Goris et al., 2017), OrthoANI (Lee et al., 2016) and Digital DNA-DNA hybridization (dDDH) and the analysis of differences in G+C content using the TYGS (Type Strain Genome Server) web server (<https://tygs.dsmz.de/>) (Meier-Kolthoff & Göker et al., 2019 Meier-Kolthoff et al., 2022). Thresholds of 95-96% for ANI and OrthoANI were used to define the bacteria at the species level (Ritcher and Roselló-Móra, 2009). An obtained value less than 70% of dDDH indicated that the species was different (Goris et al., 2007). These whole genome shotguns were deposited at GenBank under the accession identifier Bioproject PRJNA1143058 and under the following access number: GCA_041224455.1

Results

Genomic characteristics and genes involved in heavy metals resistance in *Micrococcus* sp. sma-1

The assembled genome of *Micrococcus* sp. sma-1 has 1046 contigs from 2 459 266 bp. It contains 2,333 protein-coding genes and 52 tRNA genes. The N50 and L50 were 77 473 and 213, respectively. The coverage genome was 143.5X. The percentage of G + C was 72.33 %mol (Table 1). Based on the whole genome comparison, *Micrococcus* sp. sma-1 was related to *M. luteus* group strains showing a dDDH value ranged between 73.7 % to 79.6 %. In addition, ANI and OrthoANI values were 96.86% to 97.66%. The OGRIs obtained values were greater than the proposed thresholds required from considering new species (95%-96% for ANI and OrthoANI and 70% for dDDH), indicating that the studied strain *Micrococcus* sp. sma-1 was member of *Micrococcus luteus* species (Table 2). The table 3 shows that *Micrococcus luteus* sma-1 presented 13 genes associated with resistance to several toxic metals, including mercury (3), cobalt (1), zinc (1), cadmium (1), copper (4) and iron (4). The most notable are the genes *copC*, *copD*, *merA* and *czcD*. Our results suggest that *Micrococcus luteus* sma-1 could have application in bioremediation due to its resistance to various toxic metals.

Nucleotide sequence accession numbers

The complete genome sequence of *Micrococcus luteus* sma-1 have been deposited in the NCBI under the accession number GCA_041224455.1.

Table 1. General genomic characteristics of *Micrococcus luteus* sma-1

Genome size (bp)	2 459 266
% GC	73.1
Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	61
Largest contig (bp)	147404
Mean coverage (X)	143.5
Number of reads	193 889
N50	77477
N90	22972
L50	12
L90	32
Protein-coding gene	2333
tRNA number	52
SRA accession numbers	SAMN 42993116
Assembly accession number	GCA_041224455.1

Table 2. Overall Genomic Relatedness Index between *Micrococcus luteus* sma-1 and other *Micrococcus luteus* species group

Strain	dDDH	ANI	OrthoANI	GGDC distance	G+C content difference (in%)
<i>M. yunnanensis</i> DSM 21948	79.6	97.60	97.66	0.02	0.16
<i>M. yunnanensis</i> BCRC 80243	79.5	97.60	97.66	0.02	0
<i>M. aloeverae</i> BCRC 80870	78.4	97.50	97.55	0.03	0.07
<i>M. luteus</i> NCTC 2665	73.7	96.85	96.85	0.03	0.07
<i>M. luteus</i> ATCC 4698	73.3	96.85	96.85	0.033	0.01

Table 3. Genes of *Micrococcus luteus* sma-1 found in genome related to resistance to toxic compounds

Subsystem	Gene	Protein
Mercury reductase	MIR	Mercury reductase
Mercury reductase operon	<i>merA</i>	Mercury resistance Operon regulatory protein
	<i>merR</i>	
Copper Homeostasis	CIA	Copper translocating P-type ATPase
	<i>copZ</i>	Copper chaperone
	<i>copC</i>	Copper resistance Protein CopC
	<i>copD</i>	Copper resistance Protein CopD
Cobalt-Zinc-cadmium resistance	<i>czcD</i>	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium Protein
Petrobactin-mediated iron uptake system	PB-PBP	Petrobactin ABC transporter, periplasmic binding protein
	PB-ABP_	Petrobactin ABC transporter, ATP binding protein
	PB-PII	Petrobactin ABC transporter, permease protein I
	PB-PPII	Petrobactin ABC transporter, permease protein II

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are available before their formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We welcome feedback from the community. For further information, please contact SMA (smorales@upemor.edu.mx) or BRP (broman@upemor.edu.mx).

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